

Table 1. Genera of nematodes found in deepwater rice fields near the capitals of Prajinburi (PJB) and Ayuthaya (AYT) provinces, Thailand.

Genus	In the soil before planting		Before floodwaters				After floodwater recedes				In the soil at harvest		
	PJB	AYT	soil		Root		soil		Root		PJB ^a	AYT	
			PJB	AYT	PJB	AYT	PJB	AYT	PJB	AYT			
<i>Hirschmanniella</i>	X	X	X	X	X			X	X	X	X		X
<i>Tylenchorhynchus</i>	X	X	X	X				X	X				X
<i>Meloidogyne</i>		X	X	X	X			X	X	X	X		X
<i>Helicotylenchus</i>	X	X	X	X									
<i>Tylenchus</i>	X	X	X	X									
<i>Aphelenchoides</i>		X											X
<i>Criconemoides</i>	X				X				X				X
<i>Aphelenchus</i>		X											
<i>Ditylenchus</i>		X			X				X				
<i>Pratylenchus</i>									X		X		
<i>Lengidorus</i>									X				

^aNo sampling.

Table 2. Average percentage of three genera of nematodes obtained from soil samples collected from deepwater rice fields during 1979 in Prajinburi (PJB) and Ayuthaya (AYT) provinces, Thailand.

Genus	Nematodes (av %)												Percent of total population in soil
	In the soil before planting		Before floodwater				After floodwater recedes				In the soil at harvest		
	PJB	AYT	Soil		Roots		Soil		Roots		PJB ^a	AYT	
			PJB	AYT	PJB	AYT	PJB	AYT	PJB	AYT			
<i>Hirschmanniella</i>	22.5	13.1	9.1	1.2	'few'	0	18.6	7.0	'many'	'many'	22.4		11.4
<i>Tylenchorhynchus</i>	8.1	5.7	22.1	17.7	0	0	11.8	16.1	-	-	18.5		41.5
<i>Meloidogyne</i>	-	0.4	19.9	1.0	0	0	4.0	13.6	'many'	'few'	61.0		47.1

^aNo sampling.

roots after the flood in both provinces. *Ditylenchus*, a predominant rice parasitic nematode in some countries, was found

only in Ayuthaya in small amounts. Only *Aphelenchoides* was found in the leaves, and in small numbers. Plans are

to continue this work and conduct surveys in additional provinces during the 1980 growing season. ■

Pest management and control INSECTS

Egg parasites of yellow stem borer in southern Sri Lanka

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A survey of parasites of yellow stem borer *Tryporyza incertulas* Wlk. eggs was conducted in 1979 in southern Sri Lanka. Parasites were reared from egg masses in June-July and November-December, during the major cultivation seasons. Parasitization of yellow borer egg masses averaged 88%. The parasites were identified from IBP Handbook 14 as *Trichogramma minutum* Riley,

Parasitization of yellow stem borer egg masses in southern Sri Lanka, 1979.

Location	Egg masses	
	Total sampled (no.)	Parasitization (%)
Kamburupitiya	37	86
Matara	26	81
Ambalantota	26	81
Kekanadura	69	97
Denipitiya	13	77

Tetrastichus schoenobii Ferr, *Tetrastichus israeli* M. & K, *Telenomus dignus* Gahan. *T. dignus* was the most prevalent species, occurring on more than 65% of the total egg masses counted (see table). ■

Survival of rice bug *Leptocorisa oratorius* on graminaceous weeds during the fallow period between rice cropping in Sri Lanka

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The rice bug *Leptocorisa oratorius* in both the nymphal and adult stage prevents rice grain formation by sucking the milky juice of developing grains. The ability of the pest to survive on an alternate host poses a major problem in control strategies. A survey was carried out to find the alternate hosts of the rice